

On $\delta\beta$ -Open Sets in Tri Topological Spaces

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Abstract

The main aim of this paper is to study $\delta\beta$ -open sets in tri topological spaces along with their several properties and characterizations. $\delta\beta$ -continuous and $\delta\beta$ -irresolute functions and some of their basic properties are discussed. Some new spaces in tri topological spaces, called τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - T_k spaces, $k = 1, 2, 3$ are introduced and their properties and characterizations are analyzed.

Keywords: β -interior, $\delta\beta$ -open, $\delta\beta$ -closure, $\delta\beta$ -boundary, $\delta\beta$ -continuous, $\delta\beta$ -irresolute functions.

1. Introduction

The field of mathematical science called topology is concerned with all questions directly or indirectly related to continuity. Abd El-Monsef et al. [1] presented β -open set. They also presented the concepts β -continuous and β -open mappings and gave some of their properties. Recently, β -open sets were investigated by many authors. For example, Tahiliani [12] presented an operation involving β -open sets which paved way to the creation of β - γ -open sets. Kannan and Nagaveni [4] generalized β -open set, and named it $\hat{\beta}$ -generalized closed set. Mubarki et al. [8] also generalized β -open set, and named it β^* -open set. In 2006, Hatir et al. [3] defined the concept of $\delta\beta$ -open sets in a topological space. In addition, they defined $\delta\beta$ -continuous functions to obtain a decomposition of continuity which is a generalization of δ -precontinuity. So the importance of $\delta\beta$ -continuity is that it happens to be the dual of $\delta\beta$ -continuity. In 1963, Kelly [5] introduced the concept of bitopological space. Khedr et al. [6] generalized the notion of semi preopen sets to bitopological spaces and semi pre-continuity in bitopological spaces. The concept of pre-semi open sets (open sets) was introduced by Njastad [9] in 1965. Tri topological space is a generalization of bitopological space. The study of tri topological space was first initiated by Kovar [7] in 2000, where a non-empty set X with three topologies is called tri topological space.

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In 2011, Palaniammal [10] studied the properties of open and closed sets in tri topological space. Hameed and Abid [2] introduced the definition of 123-open set in tri topological spaces. In 2016, Priyadharsini and Parvathi [11] discussed 123-semi closed sets, 123-generalized semi closed sets and some tri continuous functions in tri topological spaces. Tapi et al. [13] introduced semi open set and preopen set in tri topological space. Priyadharsini and Parvathi [11] introduced b-open set in tri topological space. U. D. Tapi and R. Sharma [10] introduced α -open set and β -open set in tri topological spaces. The topological structures were applied to rough set theory in some recent manuscripts such as [14-20].

The current work concentrates on generalization the previous near open sets and near continuous functions in tri topological spaces. The remainder of this paper is arranged as follows. In Section 2, we review the basic concepts and properties of near open sets in in tri topological spaces. The goal of Section 3 is to present the concept of $\delta\beta$ -open sets and study some of their basic properties. Relationships between the current work and the previous one [2, 5] are presented. Moreover, the concepts of $\delta\beta$ -closure and $\delta\beta$ -interior are presented. In Section 4, we propose a new class of functions on tri topological spaces called $\delta\beta$ -continuous functions and their characterizations are studied. We show that $\delta\beta$ -continuous functions are generalization of the other types of near continues functions. The basic properties of $\delta\beta$ -continuous function are investigated. Moreover, $\delta\beta$ -irresolute functions are presented and some of the basic properties are discussed. Some new spaces in tri topological spaces, called $\delta\beta$ - T_k spaces, $k = 0, 1, 2$ are introduced and their properties and characterizations are analyzed. Finally, this paper concludes in Section 5.

2. Preliminaries

This section contains the basic concepts of tri topological spaces, near tri open sets, near tri continuous and their properties.

Definition 2.1 [7] Let X be a nonempty set and τ_1, τ_2 and τ_3 be three topologies on X . The set X together with these three topologies is called a tri topological space and is denoted by (X, τ_{123}) or simply by X .

Definition 2.2 [2] A subset A of a tri topological space X is called τ_{123} -open set if $A \in \tau_1 \cup \tau_2 \cup \tau_3$ and the complement of τ_{123} -open set is τ_{123} -closed set.

Definition 2.3 [2] Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A \subseteq X$. The τ_{123} -closure and τ_{123} -interior of A (briefly, $\tau_{123} - cl(A)$ and $\tau_{123} - int(A)$) are defined, respectively, as follows:

- (i) $\tau_{123} - cl(A) = \bigcap \{F: F \supseteq A \text{ and } F \text{ is } \tau_{123} - \text{closed}\}$
- (ii) $\tau_{123} - int(A) = \bigcup \{G: G \subseteq A \text{ and } G \text{ is } \tau_{123} - \text{open}\}$

Definition 2.4 A subset A of a tri topological space (X, τ_{123}) is called,

- (a) τ_{123} -regular open [13] if $A = \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(A))$,
- (b) τ_{123} -semi open [13] if $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(A))$,
- (c) τ_{123} -preopen [13] if $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(A))$,
- (d) τ_{123} - α -open [10] if $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(A)))$,
- (e) τ_{123} - b -open [11] if $A \subseteq [\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(A))] \cup [\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(A))]$,
- (f) τ_{123} - β -open [10] if $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(A)))$,

The family of all τ_{123} -open (respectively, τ_{123} -regular open, τ_{123} -semi open, τ_{123} -preopen, τ_{123} - α -open, τ_{123} - b -open and τ_{123} - β -open) sets in a tri topological space (X, τ_{123}) is denoted by $\tau_{123}\text{-}O(X)$ (respectively, $\tau_{123}\text{-}RO(X)$, $\tau_{123}\text{-}SO(X)$, $\tau_{123}\text{-}PO(X)$, $\tau_{123}\text{-}\alpha O(X)$, $\tau_{123}\text{-}bO(X)$ and $\tau_{123}\text{-}\beta O(X)$).

Definition 2.5 Let (X, τ_{123}) and (Y, σ_{123}) be two tri topological spaces. A function $f: (X, \tau_{123}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{123})$ is said to be:

- (a) τ_{123} -semi-continuous [13] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a τ_{123} -semi-open set in X for every σ_{123} -open set V in Y .
- (b) τ_{123} -precontinuous [13] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a τ_{123} -preopen set in X for every σ_{123} -open set V in Y .
- (c) τ_{123} - α -continuous [10] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a τ_{123} - α -open set in X for every σ_{123} -open set V in Y .
- (d) τ_{123} - b -continuous [11] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a τ_{123} - b -open set in X for every σ_{123} -open set V in Y .
- (e) τ_{123} - β -continuous [10] if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a τ_{123} - β -open set in X for every σ_{123} -open set V in Y .

3. τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open and τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed sets

In this section, we present the concept of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets and study several tri topological properties of this concept. It is showed that this concept is an extension of the near tri open sets [10, 11, 13].

Definition 3.1 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and A be a subset of X . The $\tau_{123} - \delta$ -closure of A is defined by $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) = \{x \in X : A \cap \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(G)) \neq \emptyset, G \in \tau_{123} - O(X) \text{ and } x \in G\}$. A set A is called $\tau_{123} - \delta$ -closed if $A = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)$.

Notice that: $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A) = (\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A^c))^c$.

Proposition 3.1 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A \subseteq X$. Then $\tau_{123} - cl(A) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)$.

Proof. Let $x \in \tau_{123} - cl(A)$. Then $G \cap A \neq \emptyset, \forall G, x \in G, G \in \tau_{123} - O(X)$. Therefore, $A \cap G = A \cap \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - int(G)) \subseteq \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(G))$. Thus, $A \cap \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(G)) \neq \emptyset$. Hence $\tau_{123} - cl(A) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)$.

Remark 3.1 The inclusion in Proposition 3.1 cannot be replaced by equality relation as shown in the following example.

Example 3.1 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau_1 = \{X, \phi, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$, $\tau_2 = \{X, \phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}\}$, $\tau_3 = \{X, \phi, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Then, $\tau_{123} - O(X) = \{X, \phi, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. If $A = \{a\}$, then $\tau_{123} - cl(A) = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) = \{a, b, c\}$. Hence $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \not\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(A)$.

Proposition 3.2 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A, B \subseteq X$. Then, the following properties hold:

- (i) $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)$,
- (ii) If $A \subseteq B$, then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B)$,
- (iii) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cap B) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \cap \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B)$,
- (iv) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cup B) = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \cup \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B)$,

Proof. Obvious.

Remark 3.2 The equality of parts (i), (ii) and (iii) in Proposition 3.2 does not hold as shown in the following example.

Example 3.2 In Example 3.1, we have

- (i) If $A = \{a\}$, then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) = \{a, b, c\}$. Hence $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \not\subseteq A$.
- (ii) If $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{c\}$, then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B) = \{a, b, c\}$. Therefore $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B)$, but $A \not\subseteq B$.
- (iii) If $A = \{a\}$, $B = \{b\}$ and $A \cap B = \emptyset$, then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B) = \{b\}$ and $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cap B) = \emptyset$. Therefore $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \cap \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B) \not\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cap B)$.

Lemma 3.1 Let A be a subset of a tri topological space (X, τ_{123}) . Then

- (a) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \cap G \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cap G)$ for any τ_{123} - δ -open set G in X .
- (b) $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A \cup F) \subseteq \tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A) \cup F$ for any τ_{123} - δ -closed set F in X .

Definition 3.2 A subset A of a tri topological space (X, τ_{123}) is called a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open if $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)))$. The complement of a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed. The family of all τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open (resp. τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed) subsets of (X, τ_{123}) is denoted by τ_{123} - $\delta\beta O(X)$ (resp. τ_{123} - $\delta\beta C(X)$).

Theorem 3.1 The arbitrary union of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open.

Proof. Let $\{A_i : i \in I\}$ be a family of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets. Then, $A_i \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A_i)))$. Hence $\cup_i A_i \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(\cup_i A_i)))$. Consequently, $\cup_i A_i$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open.

Theorem 3.2 The arbitrary intersection of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - closed sets is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - closed.

Proof. Let $\{B_i: i \in I\}$ be a family of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed sets and $A_i = B_i^c$ for each $i \in I$. Then, $\{A_i: i \in I\}$ is a family of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets and hence $\cup_i A_i$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open. Therefore, $(\cup_i A_i)^c$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - closed. Hence, $\cap_i A_i^c$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - closed and therefore $\cap_i B_i$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - closed.

Remark 3.3 The intersection of any two τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets is not necessarily τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open as shown in the following example.

Example 3.3 In Example 3.1, if $A = \{b, c\}$ and $B = \{b, d\}$ are two τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open sets, but $A \cap B = \{b\}$ is not a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set.

The following proposition shows that τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets are stronger than τ_{123} - β -open sets. Consequently, it is stronger than of any near tri-open sets such as τ_{123} -preopen, τ_{123} -semi-open, τ_{123} - b -open, and τ_{123} - α -open sets as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The relationships between near tri-open sets.

Proposition 3.3 Every τ_{123} - β -open set is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open.

Proof. By using the properties of tri-interior, tri-closure and Proposition 3.2, the proof is obvious.

Remark 3.4 None of the implications in the above Diagram is reversible as shown by the following example.

Example 3.4 Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$, $\tau_1 = \{X, \phi, \{e\}, \{d, e\}, \{a, d, e\}\}$, $\tau_2 = \{X, \phi, \{d\}, \{e\}, \{d, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}\}$, $\tau_3 = \{X, \phi, \{d\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}\}$. Then, τ_{123} - $O(X) = \{X, \phi, \{d\}, \{e\}, \{a, d\}, \{d, e\}, \{a, d, e\}, \{b, c, e\}, \{b, c, d, e\}\}$. We have $\{b, d, e\}$ is τ_{123} $\delta\beta$ - open but not τ_{123} - regular open. Also, $\{a, e\}$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open but not τ_{123} - preopen. $\{c\}$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open but not τ_{123} - β -open. $\{b\}$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open but not τ_{123} -semi-open. $\{c, d\}$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open but not τ_{123} - α -open.

Definition 3.3 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A \subseteq X$. The τ_{123} $\delta\beta$ -closure and τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -interior of A (briefly, $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)$ and $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A)$) are defined, respectively, as follows:

- (i) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) = \cap \{F: F \supseteq A \text{ and } F \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta C(X)\}$,
- (ii) $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) = \cup \{G: G \subseteq A \text{ and } G \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta O(X)\}$.

Some properties of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closure and τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -interior follow throughout the next results.

Proposition 3.4 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space, if A and B are two subsets of X , then the following properties hold:

- (a) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(X) = \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(X) = X$ and $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(\emptyset) = \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(\emptyset) = \emptyset$,
- (b) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)$ (resp. $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A)$) is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed (resp. τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open),
- (c) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)$ (resp. $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A)$) is the smallest (resp. largest) τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed (resp. τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open) set which contains (resp. contained in) A ,
- (d) A is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed (resp. τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open) if and only if $A = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)$ (resp. $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A)$),
- (e) If $A \subseteq B$, then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(B)$ and $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) \subseteq \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(B)$,
- (f) $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) \subseteq A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)$,
- (g) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)) = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)$, and $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A)) = \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A)$,
- (h) $x \in \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A)$ if and only if for each a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set G containing x , $G \cap A \neq \emptyset$,
- (i) $x \in \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A)$ if and only if there exist τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set W such that $x \in W \subseteq A$,
- (j) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) \cup \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(B) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A \cup B)$,
- (k) $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A \cap B) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) \cap \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(B)$,
- (l) $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A \cap B) \subseteq \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) \cap \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(B)$,
- (m) $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) \cup \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(B) \subseteq \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A \cup B)$.

Proof. Straightforward.

The equality of parts (j), (k), (l) and (m) in Proposition 3.4 are not hold as shown in the following example.

Example 3.5 In Example 3.1, we have:

- (j) If $A = \{a, c\}$ and $B = \{a, d\}$, then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) = \{a, c\}$, $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(B) = \{a, d\}$ and $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A \cup B) = X$. Hence $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A \cup B) \not\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) \cup \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(B)$.
- (k) If $A = \{a, c, d\}$ and $B = \{b, c, d\}$, then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) = X$, $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(B) = \{b, c, d\}$ and $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A \cap B) = \{c, d\}$. Hence $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) \cap \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(B) \not\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A \cap B)$.
- (l) If $A = \{b, c\}$ and $B = \{b, d\}$, then $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) = \{b, c\}$, $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(B) = \{b, d\}$ and $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A \cap B) = \emptyset$. Hence $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) \cap \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(B) \not\subseteq \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A \cap B)$.
- (m) If $A = \{a\}$ and $B = \{c\}$, then $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) = \{a\}$, $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(B) = \emptyset$ and $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A \cup B) = \{a, c\}$. Hence $\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A \cup B) \not\subseteq \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A) \cup \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(B)$.

Theorem 3.3 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A \subseteq X$. Then

- (i) $(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A))^c = \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A^c)$,
- (ii) $(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A))^c = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A^c)$.

Proof. Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A \subseteq X$,

- (i) Since, $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A) = \cap \{F: F \supseteq A \text{ and } F \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta C(X)\}$
 $(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A))^c = (\cap \{F: F \supseteq A \text{ and } F \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta C(X)\})^c$
 $= \cup \{F^c: F^c \subseteq A^c \text{ and } F^c \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta O(X)\}$
 $= \tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A^c)$.
- (ii) Similarly, $(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta\beta}(A))^c = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta\beta}(A^c)$.

Proposition 3.5 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A, B \subseteq X$. If $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)$ and B be a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open set, then A is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open.

Proof. Let $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)$ and B be a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set. Then $\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) = \tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B)$. Thus, $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B))) = \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)))$ and hence A is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open.

Proposition 3.6 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A, B \subseteq X$. If $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_{123}$ - $cl(A)$ and A is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set, then B is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open

Proof. Let $A \subseteq B \subseteq \tau_{123}$ - $cl(A)$ and A be a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set. Then, $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)))$. Since $B \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(A)$, then $B \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)))) = \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A))) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(B)))$. Thus B is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open.

Corollary 3.1 Let $(X, \tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3)$ be a tri topological space. If A is a $\tau_1\tau_2\tau_3$ - $\delta\beta$ -open, then $\tau_1\tau_2\tau_3$ - $cl(A)$ is $\tau_1\tau_2\tau_3$ - $\delta\beta$ -open.

Proposition 3.7 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A \subseteq X$ be a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed set if and only if τ_{123} - $int(\tau_{123}$ - $cl(\tau_{123}$ - $int_{\delta}(A))) \subseteq A$

Proof. Let A be a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed $\Leftrightarrow X - A$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open

$$\begin{aligned} &\Leftrightarrow X - A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(X - A))) \\ &= \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(X - \tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A))) \\ &= \tau_{123} - cl(X - \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A))) \\ &= X - \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A))) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A))) \subseteq A \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space. A subset A of X is said to be τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha$ -open if $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(A)))$. The complement of a $\tau_1\tau_2\tau_3$ - $\delta\alpha$ -open set is a $\tau_1\tau_2\tau_3$ - $\delta\alpha$ -closed.

The family of all τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha$ -open (resp. τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha$ -closed) sets of X is denoted by τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha O(X)$ (resp. τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha C(X)$).

It is obvious that every τ_{123} - δ -open set is τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha$ -open.

Proposition 3.8 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space. If A is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open and B is τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha$ -open then $A \cap B$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open.

Proof. Let A be τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open and B is τ_{123} - $\delta\alpha$ -open. Then, $A \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A)))$ and $B \subseteq \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(B)))$, respectively. This implies that

$$\begin{aligned} A \cap B &\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A))) \cap \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(B))) \\ &\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int((\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A))) \cap (\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(B)))))) \\ &\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A) \cap \tau_{123} - int_{\delta}(B)))) \\ &\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cap B)))) \\ &\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cap B)))) \\ &= \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_{\delta}(A \cap B))) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $A \cap B$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set.

Corollary 3.2 A set A in a tri topological space (X, τ_{123}) is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open if and only if $G \cap A \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta O(X)$, for every τ_{123} - δ - open set G of X .

Proof. Let A be τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open set. Then

$$\begin{aligned} G \cap A &\subseteq G \cap \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_\delta(A))) \\ &= \tau_{123} - int(G) \cap \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_\delta(A))) \\ &\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl((\tau_{123} - int(G)) \cap \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_\delta(A))) \\ &= \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(G \cap \tau_{123} - cl_\delta(A))) \\ &\subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl_\delta(G \cap A))) \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 3.1, we get $G \cap A \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta O(X)$.

4. $\tau_{123} - \delta\beta$ -continuous function in tritopological spaces

The notion of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - continuous functions is introduced in this section. It is a generalization of the other types of near tri continuous functions [10,11,13]. The main properties and characterizations of this new type of near tri continuous functions are studied.

Definition 4.1 A function $f: (X, \tau_{123}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{123})$ is said to be τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous if $f^{-1}(V)$ is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - open set in X for every σ_{123} - open set V in Y .

Proposition 4.1 The following statements are equivalent for a function $f: (X, \tau_{123}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{123})$:

- (1) f is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous,
- (2) For each $x \in X$ and each σ_{123} -open set Z of Y containing $f(x)$, there exist $W \in \tau_{123}$ - $\delta\beta O(X)$ containing x such that $f(W) \subseteq Z$,
- (3) The inverse image of each σ_{123} -closed set in Y is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed in X ,
- (4) $\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - (int_\delta(f^{-1}(B)))) \subseteq f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B))$, for each subset B of Y ,
- (5) $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B)) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - (cl_\delta(f^{-1}(B))))$, for each subset B of Y ,
- (6) $\tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B))$, for each subset B of Y ,
- (7) $f(\tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(A)) \subseteq \sigma_{123} - cl(f(A))$, for each subset A of X ,
- (8) $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B)) \subseteq \tau_{123} - \delta\beta-int(f^{-1}(B))$, for each subset B of Y .

Proof. (1) \Leftrightarrow (2) and (1) \Leftrightarrow (3) are obvious.

(3) \Rightarrow (4). Let B be any subset of Y . Then, by (3) $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B))$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed. Hence $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B)) \supseteq \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - (int_\delta(f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B)))) \supseteq \tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int_\delta(f^{-1}(B))))$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5). By replacing $V \setminus B$ instead of B in (4), we have

$\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - (int_\delta(f^{-1}(V \setminus B)))) \subseteq f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(V \setminus B))$ and therefore $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B)) \subseteq \tau_{123} - cl(\tau_{123} - int(\tau_{123} - (cl_\delta(f^{-1}(B))))$, for each subset B of Y .

(5) \Rightarrow (1). Obvious.

(3) \Rightarrow (6). Let B be any subset of Y and $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B))$ be τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed in X . Then $\tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq \tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B))) = f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(B))$

(6) \Rightarrow (7). Let A be any subset of X . Then $f(A) \subseteq Y$ by (6), we have $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(f(A))) \supseteq \tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(f^{-1}(f(A))) \supseteq \tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(A)$. Therefore, $\sigma_{123} - cl(f(A)) \supseteq f f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - cl(f(A))) \supseteq f(\tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(A))$.

(7) \Rightarrow (3). Let F be any closed set of Y . Then $f^{-1}(F) = f^{-1}(cl(F))$. Hence by (7), $f(\tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(f^{-1}(F))) \subseteq \sigma_{123} - cl(f(f^{-1}(F))) \subseteq \sigma_{123} - cl(F) = F$, thus $\tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(f^{-1}(F)) \subseteq f^{-1}(F)$, so, $f^{-1}(F) = \tau_{123} - \delta\beta-cl(f^{-1}(F))$. Therefore, $f^{-1}(F) \in \tau_{123} - \delta\beta C(X)$.

(1) \Rightarrow (8). Let B be any subset of Y . Then $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B))$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open in X . Thus, $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B)) = \tau_{123} - \delta\beta - int(f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B))) \subseteq \tau_{123} - \delta\beta - int(f^{-1}(B))$. Therefore, $f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B)) \subseteq \tau_{123} - \delta\beta - int(f^{-1}(B))$.

(8) \Rightarrow (1). For any open set B of Y , by (8), $f^{-1}(B) = f^{-1}(\sigma_{123} - int(B)) \subseteq \tau_{123} - \delta\beta-int(f^{-1}(B))$. Hence, $f^{-1}(B)$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open in X . Therefore, f is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous.

The relationships between τ_{123} - β -continuous and τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous functions are clearly by the following remark.

Remark 4.1 Every τ_{123} - β -continuous is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous.

The converse of Remark 4.1 is not true as per the following example.

Example 4.1 Let $X = \{1,2,3,4\}$, $\tau_1 = \{X, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,2,3\}\}$, $\tau_2 = \{X, \emptyset, \{3\}, \{1,3\}, \{1,3,4\}\}$, $\tau_3 = \{X, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{1,4\}, \{1,2,4\}\}$. Then $\tau_{123} - O(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,3\}, \{1,4\}, \{1,2,4\}, \{1,2,3\}, \{1,3,4\}\}$. Let $Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\sigma_1 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{c\}, \{a, c\}\}$, $\sigma_2 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{c, d\}\}$, $\sigma_3 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Then $\sigma_{123} - O(Y) = \{Y, \emptyset, \{c\}, \{d\}, \{a, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(1) = a$, $f(2) = b$, $f(3) = c$ and $f(4) = d$. f is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous function, but it is not τ_{123} - β -continuous since $\{d\} \in \sigma_{123} - O(Y)$ but $f^{-1}(\{d\}) = \{4\} \notin \tau_{123} - \beta O(X)$.

The relationships between the different types of near tri continuous functions is shown in the following diagram,

Figure 2: The relationships the different types of near tri continuous functions.

Remark 4.2 None of the implications in the above Diagram is reversible as shown by the following examples.

Example 4.2 Let $X = \{1,2,3,4\}$, $\tau_1 = \{X, \emptyset, \{3,4\}, \{1,3,4\}\}$, $\tau_2 = \{X, \emptyset, \{3\}, \{1,3\}\}$, $\tau_3 = \{X, \emptyset, \{4\}, \{3,4\}\}$. Then $\tau_{123} - O(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{3\}, \{4\}, \{1,3\}, \{3,4\}, \{1,3,4\}\}$, $Y = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\sigma_1 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{a, c\}\}$, $\sigma_2 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{a, b, c\}\}$, $\sigma_3 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Then $\sigma_{123} - O(Y) = \{Y, \emptyset, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(1) = a$, $f(2) = b$, $f(3) = c$ and $f(4) = d$. Then f is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous function, but it is not τ_{123} -continuous, τ_{123} - α -continuous neither τ_{123} -pre-continuous.

Example 4.3 Let $X = \{1,2,3\}$, $\tau_1 = \{X, \emptyset, \{1\}\}$, $\tau_2 = \{X, \emptyset, \{1,2\}\}$, $\tau_3 = \{X, \emptyset, \{1,3\}\}$. Then $\tau_{123} - O(X) = \{X, \emptyset, \{1\}, \{1,2\}, \{1,3\}\}$, $Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\sigma_1 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{a\}\}$, $\sigma_2 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{b\}\}$, $\sigma_3 = \{Y, \emptyset, \{a, b\}\}$. Then $\sigma_{123} - O(Y) = \{Y, \emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(1) = c$, $f(2) = b$ and $f(3) = a$. Then f is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous function, but it is not τ_{123} -semi continuous, τ_{123} - b -continuous neither τ_{123} - β -continuous.

Definition 4.2 Let (X, τ_{123}) be a tri topological space and $A \subseteq U$. A space X is said to be

- (a) τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - T_0 if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exists a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set U , such that either $x \in U$, $y \notin U$ or $y \in U$, $x \notin U$.
- (b) τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - T_1 if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exist τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets U and V containing x and y , respectively, such that $y \notin U$ and $x \notin V$.
- (c) τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - T_2 (τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -Hausdorff) if for each pair of distinct points x and y in X , there exist τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $y \in V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$.

Proposition 4.2 Let (X, τ_{123}) and (Y, σ_{123}) be two tri topological spaces and $f: (X, \tau_{123}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{123})$ be a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous injection. Then the following properties hold

- (a) If Y is a σ_{123} -Hausdorff space, then X is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -Hausdorff,
- (b) If Y is a σ_{123} - T_1 -space, then X is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - T_1 .

Proof. (a) By the injectivity of f , $f(x) \neq f(y)$ for any distinct points x and y in X . Since Y is a σ_{123} -Hausdorff space, there exist σ_{123} -open sets A and B containing $f(x)$ and $f(y)$, respectively, such that $A \cap B = \emptyset$. Since f is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous, there exist τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets C and D containing x and y , respectively, such that $f(C) \subseteq A$ and $f(D) \subseteq B$ such that $C \cap D = \emptyset$. That is, X is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -Hausdorff.

(b) Since f is injective and Y is a σ_{123} - T_1 -space, for $x \neq y$ in X , there exist σ_{123} -open sets $A, B \subseteq Y$ such that $f(x) \in A$, $f(y) \notin A$ and $f(x) \notin B$, $f(y) \in B$. Since f is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous, $f^{-1}(A)$ and $f^{-1}(B)$ are τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open subsets of X such that $x \in f^{-1}(A)$, $y \notin f^{-1}(A)$ and $x \notin f^{-1}(B)$, $y \in f^{-1}(B)$. That is, X is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - T_1 .

Definition 4.3 Let (X, τ_{123}) and (Y, σ_{123}) be two tri topological spaces. A function $f: (X, \tau_{123}) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_{123})$ is called τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -irresolute if $f^{-1}(Z)$ is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set of X for every σ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set Z of Y .

Proposition 4.3 Every τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -irresolute function is τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous.

Proof. Follows from the definitions.

The following example shows that the converse of the above proposition is not true in general

Example 4.4 Let $X = \{1,2,3\}$, $\tau_1 = \{X, \phi, \{1\}\}$, $\tau_2 = \{X, \phi, \{2\}\}$, $\tau_3 = \{X, \phi, \{1,2\}\}$. Then τ_{123} - $O(X) = \{X, \phi, \{1\}, \{2\}, \{1,2\}\}$. Let $Y = \{a, b, c\}$, $\sigma_1 = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}\}$, $\sigma_2 = \{Y, \phi, \{a, b\}\}$, $\sigma_3 = \{Y, \phi, \{a, c\}\}$. Then σ_{123} - $O(Y) = \{Y, \phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}\}$. Define $f: X \rightarrow Y$ by $f(1) = b$, $f(2) = a$, and $f(3) = c$. Then f is a τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous function, but it is not τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -irresolute since $\{c\} \in \tau_{123}$ - $\delta\beta O(Y)$ but $f^{-1}(\{c\}) = \{3\} \notin \tau_{123}$ - $\delta\beta O(X)$.

5. Conclusion

This paper presented a study of new structure in tri topological spaces which was τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open sets. These sets were generalized the usual notions of near open sets. Since, the class of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open set was stronger than any type of the previous classes of near open sets such as, τ_{123} -regular open set, τ_{123} - α -open set, τ_{123} -semi open set, τ_{123} -preopen set and τ_{123} - β -open set, etc. Several topological characterizations and properties of the current new sort of sets were studied. Additionally, the concepts of near continues functions were extended to τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous functions. It was showed that every τ_{123} - β -continuous function was τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous function. Therefore, τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous functions were generalization of the other types of near continues functions. The basic properties of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -continuous function were investigated. Moreover, τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -irresolute functions were presented and some of the basic properties were discussed. Some new spaces in tri topological spaces, called τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ - T_k spaces, $k = 0, 1, 2$ were introduced and their properties and characterizations were analyzed. In our future work, we will go on studying separation axioms, compactness, connectedness, etc. of τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ in tri topological spaces. And will study soft τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -open and τ_{123} - $\delta\beta$ -closed in soft tri topological space to carry out general framework for applications in practical life.

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